

Stephen King At Work

Vincent Neyt, University of Antwerp

Vincent on the Kingsize podcast

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I had a long and lovely talk about the project with Matt and Simon of **Kingsize**, a Stephen King podcast based in the UK. The episode is called “Insights With Stephen King scholar Vincent Neyt”. It can be found on all podcast platforms, or via this link:

**Kingsize Insights
With Stephen King
scholar Vincent Neyt**

<https://anchor.fm/kingsizepodcast/episodes/Kingsize-Insights-With-Stephen-King-scholar-Vincent-Neyt-e1kueoo>

